

Political Implications of Globalization of Business and Management Education

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ABSTRACT

Education, particularly higher education in India is undergoing rapid changes under the impact of Globalization. In today's globalized environment, education has become more valuable to individuals. Education provides individuals with a better chance of employment, which in turn leads to a better lifestyle, power and status. India has the third largest higher education system in the world. Keeping this point in their mind, many foreign universities are wishing to set up their shops particularly in business and management education in India. The Indian press reports that 40 international universities have sought land from the Government of Maharashtra to establish campuses in that state. The motivation behind this is very clear- everyone who enters the Indian educational market wants to extract profits mostly by offering academic programmes in fields that are in high demand. Before allowing foreign institutions to set up their branches in India, government should address a number of core issues like what is the motivation of the foreign institutions? What is the status of the foreign institutions in its own country? Is the foreign institution capable of offering the same quality in India as it does at home? Is everything about the foreign branch transparent and open? Does the foreign institution have appropriate infrastructures such as libraries, e-learning, facilities and laboratories to deliver the programmes it proposed? Taking all these factors into considerations, this paper purely discusses the political implications of Globalization of Business and Management Education.

KEY WORDS: Globalization, Education, Quality, Political, Motivation, Implications,

1. Introduction

The political implications of Globalization of Business and Management Education manifest itself in a number of ways. The first and most important is a very close relationship between the business icons and government. Second, Business and Management schools have also become sources of political power in

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local areas. Many business schools have been founded by politicians to increase their influence in society. In such an atmosphere, the educational aspects of the institutions are bound to suffer. Political pressures in appointments to boards of studies, custodian of examination and other posts in business and management institutions are more the rule than the exception. So one might ask in the area of globalization, how is the current situation to be improved? One must also know how to change and what aspects of the system require alteration or reform? The main purpose of this paper is to identify the political implications of Globalization of Business and Management Education.

2. Objectives of the study:

The following are the important objectives of the study. They are as follows

- i. To identify political implications of business and management education.
- ii. To examine the challenges before the government in the present scenario of globalization of business and management education.
- iii. To evaluate the motivation of foreign institutions entering into the Indian educational market.

3. Methodology

This paper is purely in descriptive in nature. It is mainly based on secondary data and is largely collected from different sources like books, journals, articles and periodicals. In addition to all these, the articles and editorials written in the leading newspapers have been referred.

4. Analysis and Findings

Providing higher education in general and business and management education in particular is a difficult task in a globalised world. Providing higher education means confronting social inequalities deeply rooted in Indian society. Philip G. Altbach in his article 'The Global Academic Revolution- Implications for India' states that geography, unequal distribution of wealth and resources all contribute to the disadvantage of certain population group. The Indian government reserved certain seats in universities for disadvantaged groups. But participation of lower castes, rural populations and Muslims continue to lag behind the general population.

Indian bureaucracy enjoys lot of powers in higher educational sector without any accountability. It lacks accountability but its control over higher education is very strong. Altbach has rightly observed that it is impossible to build world class universities in this bureaucratic context. If the new institutions must tolerate

responsibilities to both the central government and the states in which they are located, the bureaucratic burden will be completely overwhelming. Bureaucracy governs everything and academics have little powers in these matters.

Since independence higher education is not the first priority of the government. It does not spend much money on higher education. According to Altbach “Less than one percent of GDP is spent on education compared to five percent recommended by many experts. Developed countries typically spend around 5 percent. If higher education is to provide both high qualities at the top and mass access at the bottom, significantly more must be spent.”

Quality assurance is considered central to any successful higher education system. It is unfortunate to say that quality assurance is largely ineffective in India. India’s arrangements do not encourage quality. The central government agencies are mainly responsible for supporting higher education. But central agencies like UGC/ AICTE have been widely criticized for their ineffectiveness. India needs to address these issues very effectively.

According to Philip G. Altbach “India has a large private higher education sector that has traditionally been heavily subsidized by the state and tightly controlled by the public universities. This situation is changing. There are now a number of private universities that are largely free of government control and receive no public funds. The unsubsidized private higher education sector is rapidly expanding ensuring that it can serve a public purpose will be a challenge.”

Philip G. Altbach identified the following implications of globalization.

- i. Research universities likely to receive serious setbacks.
- ii. The system will face pressures to establish or increase tuition fees for students.
- iii. Cost-cutting practices at many universities will result in a deterioration of quality. More part-time faculty is likely to be hired, class sizes increased and other savings implemented.

5. Limitations of the study

The study is limited to one aspect of the subject i.e. the political implications of globalization of business and management education. It is entirely based on secondary data i.e. books, journals, periodicals, newspapers etc. This constitutes a major constraint of the study as the journals; periodicals are sometimes subject to manipulations and information available in them is in historical in nature.

6. Conclusion and suggestions

The political implications of Globalization of Business and Management Education clearly indicates that

- i. Globalization of business and management education contribute to the disadvantage of certain population group mainly lower castes, rural population and minorities.
- ii. Bureaucracy governs everything in India and it has no accountability.
- iii. Higher education is not the first priority of the government.
- iv. Quality assurance is largely ineffective in India.
- v. Research universities receive serious setbacks.
- vi. Cost-cutting practices may result in a deterioration of quality.

It is true that India cannot keep its academic doors closed. Because India is also a central part of globalised world. Philip G. Altbach in his article "Is Open Door in Higher Education Desirable?" rightly pointed out that India needs a clear and transparent policy and regulatory frame work. A regulatory body is essential for selecting, monitoring and evaluating foreign institutions. Without regulatory framework opening the doors will create long term problems for India's academic problem.

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